

9 Application of hollow fiber liquid phase microextraction for simultaneous
10 determination of regulated and emerging iodinated trihalomethanes in
11 drinking water

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26 **Abstract**

27 Trihalomethanes (THMs) are regulated disinfection by-products (DBPs) most commonly analyzed in
28 quality control water supply due to their harmful effects on health. However, few data exist about the content of
29 emerging iodo-trihalomethanes (I-THMs) which are present in drinking water at very low concentrations (in the
30 order of ng L^{-1}). For this reason a two-phase hollow fiber liquid phase microextraction method for the
31 simultaneous determination of four regulated trihalomethanes and six emerging iodo-trihalomethanes using
32 GC- μ ECD and GC-MS with detection limits in the range of few ng L^{-1} has been developed. A central
33 composite design was used to optimize conditions for simultaneous extraction. The best extraction recovery
34 was obtained with 19.2 min at 27.1°C and 900 rpm, without salt addition, using a supported hollow fiber
35 membrane of 10.5 cm (0.6 mm id) and 1-octanol as acceptor phase. The limits of detection for the regulated
36 THMs and I-THMs were 3-44 ng L^{-1} and 1-3 ng L^{-1} respectively. The calibration curves showed good linearity
37 ($r^2 > 0.995$) and good repeatability (3-22%). The relative recoveries in water were between 96.5% to 105.2%.

38 The method was applied for the simultaneous determination of trihalomethanes in supply water samples
39 from seven water distribution systems (WDS) in the Huelva area, located at the southwest Spain, which use
40 different water-treatment processes. The highest concentrations of I-THMs, particularly CHBrClI and CHCl_2I ,
41 were detected in water treated with advanced treatment process using pre-ozonation, however these compounds
42 were not detected or decreased along distribution system. In the samples of treated water with conventional
43 treatment, using pre-oxidation by permanganate and distribution network, CHCl_2I , CHBrClI , CHClI_2 , CHBrI_2

44 and CHI_3 were detected at very low concentrations ($1\text{-}18\text{ ng L}^{-1}$). Finally, in water samples from underground
45 origin without oxidation treatment, in which only disinfection with sodium hypochlorite was applied, I-THMs
46 were not detected.

47 **Keywords**

48 Iodo-Trihalomethanes, Hollow fiber membrane, Gas chromatography, Disinfection by-products, Drinking
49 water.

50 **1. Introduction**

51 Drinking water chlorination plays an important role in preventing pathogen contamination that
52 causes water-borne diseases. However, chemical disinfection with chlorine leads to the formation of
53 disinfection by products (DBPs) due to reaction with natural organic matter (NOM), which can cause
54 potential health problems [1]. Epidemiologic investigations have demonstrated the association
55 between exposure to DBPs present in drinking water and cancer (bladder [2], colon [3] stomach,
56 pancreas, kidney and rectum) [4,5], as well as adverse birth outcomes [6,7]. THMs exposure may also
57 contribute to increased risk of Hodgkin and non-Hodgkin lymphoma [8] and spontaneous abortion. Up
58 to now, about 600–700 DBPs have been identified in drinking water [1], but only few DBPs have
59 been evaluated for adverse effects. Therefore, only a limited number of regulations and guidelines
60 have been established for DBPs, which include four trihalomethanes (THMs: chloroform, bromoform,
61 bromodichloromethane, and chlorodibromomethane) and five haloacetic acids (HAAs:
62 monochloroacetic acid, dichloroacetic acid, trichloroacetic acid, monobromoacetic acid and
63 dibromoacetic acid) [9,10].

64 Iodinated DBPs (I-DBPs) include iodo-acids and iodo-trihalomethanes that have been
65 identified in drinking water from ng L^{-1} to low $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ levels. I-THMs have been described as powerful
66 cytotoxics [11], and recent studies have demonstrated that iodinated DBPs had more cytotoxic and
67 genotoxic effects than their brominated and chlorinated analogues, due to the stronger leaving
68 potential of iodine atom. Iodoform (CHI_3) was considered the most cytotoxic compound, and
69 chlorodiodomethane (CHClI_2) as the most genotoxic I-THMs species [12]. Additionally, mammalian
70 cell toxicity results provided evidence for the toxicity of iodinated DBPs because iodoform (CHI_3)
71 was 60 times and 146 times more cytotoxic than bromoform (CHBr_3) and chloroform (CHCl_3),
72 respectively [13]. In addition to their toxicity, I-THMs have very low odor and taste thresholds,
73 especially iodoform (CHI_3), which at concentrations above $0.1\text{ }\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ water provides a characteristic
74 medicinal smell [14].

75 Different analytical methods have been reported for analysis of regulated THMs in drinking
76 water, but gas chromatography (GC) coupled with electron capture detection (ECD) or mass

77 spectrometry (MS) are widely used. ECD detector is generally more sensitive than mass spectrometry
78 (MS) for halogenated organic compounds, although MS detector is more selective to confirm the
79 compounds detected in the samples [15].

80 Many of these methods study critically analyte extraction techniques or the introduction of the
81 sample into the GC. Conventional liquid–liquid extraction (LLE) [16-19], purge and trap [20-24],
82 direct aqueous injection (DAI) [25-27], static headspace (HS) [28-30], solid-phase microextraction
83 (SPME) [31,32], solid-phase extraction [33], headspace solid-phase microextraction (HS-SPME)
84 [34-37], liquid-phase microextraction (LPME) [38,39], headspace-liquid-phase microextraction (HS-
85 LPME) [40,41], hollow fiber membrane (HF-LPME) [42,43] and dispersive liquid–liquid
86 microextraction (DLLME) [44,45], have been used to monitor regulated THMs species in drinking
87 water.

88 Low concentrations of I-THMs in water samples require inclusion of optimal pre-concentration
89 step before the gas chromatography analysis, such as liquid–liquid extraction (LLE) [12,46,47]. An
90 alternative method to extract and concentrate analytes from water samples is the use of solid-phase
91 microextraction (SPME) [47,48,49].

92 Milton-Moreano et al. compared HS-SPME, HF-LPME and HS extraction for determination of
93 trihalomethanes in drinking water by gas chromatography electron capture detector and mass
94 spectrometry detection. As result, the HF-LPME–GC–ECD method proved to be the most sensitive
95 for determination of regulated THMs compounds, with a very high concentration factor, low LOD,
96 good accuracy and precision [43].

97 Due to the increased interest in monitoring the occurrence of I-DBPs in water, analytical
98 methods for the simultaneous quantification of chloro, bromo and iodo-trihalomethanes are necessary.
99 Recently S. Allard et al. developed a HS SPME-GC/MS method for simultaneous analysis of 10
100 THMs (4 regulated, chlorinated and brominated compounds and 6 unregulated iodinated ones) with
101 detection limits ranging from 1 ng/L for iodoform to 20 ng L⁻¹ for chloroform [50].

102 In this work a new analytical method for the simultaneous determination of the ten
103 trihalomethanes present drinking water based on supported liquid hollow fiber membrane
104 microextraction (HF-LPME) and GC- μ ECD was developed. In addition confirmation of compounds
105 in the samples was performed by GC-MS. A remarkable advantage of this chromatographic approach
106 is the combination of the sensitivity of electron capture detector with the selectivity of the mass
107 spectrometer to get low detection limits and unequivocal identification of the analytes. The developed

108 method is simple, reproducible and cheap, reaching low detection limits that makes the approach
109 suitable for routine laboratories control in water distribution systems.

110 **2. Experimental. Material and methods**

111 **2.1. Chemicals and solutions**

112 All reagents used were of highest purity, iodoform (CHI_3), 1,2 dibromopropane (used as internal
113 standard SI) and THMs mixture $100 \mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$ of each compound: chloroform (CHCl_3),
114 bromodichloromethane (CHBrCl_2), dibromochloromethane (CHBr_2Cl), and bromoform (CHBr_3), were
115 purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim Germany). Iodo-trihalomethanes (I-THMs):
116 bromodiiodomethane (CHBrI_2 90%), bromochloriodomethane (CHBrClI 95%), chlorodiiodomethane
117 (CHClI_2 95%), dibromiodomethane (CHBr_2I 95%) and dichloriodomethane (CHCl_2I 95%) were
118 purchased from Orchid Cellmark (New Westminster, BC, Canada). Methanol, n-hexane, toluene,
119 acetonitrile and acetone were purchased from Teknokroma (Barcelona, Spain). n-Octanol was
120 supplied from Merck (Barcelona, Spain).

121 Accurel Q 3/2 polypropylene hollow fiber membranes with an inner diameter of $600 \mu\text{m}$, $200 \mu\text{m}$
122 of wall thickness and $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ pore size was obtained from Wuppertal (Germany). Ultrapure water
123 ($18\text{M}\Omega \text{ cm}$) was obtained from a Milli-Q water-purification system (Millipore, Watford, UK) and was
124 used for spiked samples and blanks preparation.

125 Standard stock, intermediate and work solutions of each regulated THMs (chloroform,
126 bromodichloromethane, dibromochloromethane and bromoform) were prepared in methanol at 20 mg
127 L^{-1} , $200 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and $5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively. Standard stock, intermediate and work solutions of each I-
128 THMs (iodoform, bromodiiodomethane, bromochloriodomethane, chlorodiiodomethane,
129 dibromiodomethane and dichloriodomethane) were prepared in methanol at 10 mg L^{-1} , $10 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$
130 and $1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively. Stock and intermediate solutions were stored into the dark at $-20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for a
131 maximum of one month. Work standard solutions were prepared daily in ultra pure water. The internal
132 standard (IS) solution (1,2-dibromopropane) was prepared in methanol at a concentration of 5 mg L^{-1}
133 to achieve a final concentration of $5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.

134 **2.2. Sample collection**

135 Water samples were taken in twelve sampling points from seven different water distribution
136 systems. The sampling points were defined in finished water reservoirs of six water treatment plants
137 (S1, S2, S3, S4, S5 and S6), in two water reservoirs of underground origin and disinfection treatment
138 (S7 and S8), and four water reservoirs of the corresponding distribution systems (S2.1, S3.1, S3.2 and
139 S4.1).

140 Water samples include five finished water from WTPs with conventional treatment: Aljaraque
141 (S1), Lepe (S2), Riotinto (S4), Encinasola (S5) and Cumbres San Bartolomé (S6), one sample of
142 finished water from Lepe WTP with advanced treatment (S3), two treated water from underground
143 origen with disinfection treatment: Jabugo (S7) and Hinojales (S8) reservoirs, and four samples water
144 from reservoirs of corresponding distribution systems: Ayamonte (S2.1 and S3.1), Isla Canela (S3.2)
145 and Fuente la Corcha (S4.1). Sampling program with the characteristics of the water distribution
146 systems and sample points are shown in Fig. S1 and Table S1 in the Supplementary Information.

147 Samples were collected from the tap of each sample point. Before collecting tap water samples, the
148 tap was opened for 5 min to assure the representativeness of the sample. The samples were collected
149 into 125 mL amber glass bottles with teflon-lined screw caps, containing 1.5 mL of sodium thiosulfate
150 solution 0.1 M to eliminate any residual chlorine and to prevent additional DBP formation during
151 transportation to the laboratory. Samples were stored at 4 °C until analysis.

152 **2.3. Hollow-fiber liquid phase microextraction (HF-LPME)**

153 The configuration of the supported hollow fiber membrane liquid microextraction system is based
154 on other described previously elsewhere [42, 51-53], which is illustrated in Fig. 1. The hollow fiber
155 was cut into pieces of 10.5 cm length and cleaned with acetone to remove any possible contaminant.
156 The fiber was removed and allowed to be completely dry. To carry out the extraction, one end of the
157 cleaned fiber was attached to a medical syringe needle (inner diameter of 0.7 mm x 50 mm). Then, 1
158 mL of solvent was passed through the fiber to ensure that the lumen of membrane was filled with the
159 organic phase. The other end of the fiber was joined to another medical syringe needle that were
160 connected to the syringe body, acting as a cap to prevent the solvent loss during extraction. After that,
161 the U-shaped fiber system was immersed into an extracting organic solvent for around two minutes to
162 impregnate the fiber pores with the organic solvent. The U-shaped fiber was placed into the aqueous
163 sample (20 mL) for extraction. Then the fiber was removed from the donor solution and dried with a
164 piece of paper to eliminate trace of water. One end of the fiber was detached from the medical syringe
165 needle and the extracting solvent was flushed by an air blow from the syringe into a microvial. The
166 extract obtained was collected into a 1.5 mL vial attached to a 250 μ L insert. A total of 4 μ L of the
167 organic extract was transferred to another GC vial containing 16 μ L of n-hexane (extract:n-hexane
168 ratio 20:80). Finally, 1 μ L of this solution was injected into the GC- μ ECD. The extraction was
169 performed during 19.2 min at 27.1 °C and 900 rpm.

170 **2.4. Gas chromatographic analysis**

171 The extracts were analysed in a Agilent 6890N gas chromatograph system with a 63 Ni
172 microelectron capture detector (GC- μ ECD) (Hewlett Packard, Wilmington, DE, USA). Initially the

173 chromatographic conditions were optimized to achieve the highest peak areas, good chromatographic
174 resolution and suitable integration. A DB-5 chromatographic column (30m x 0.25mm x 0.25 μ m J&C
175 Scientific) was used. Helium (99.999 %) was used as carrier gas with a flow rate of 1.2 ml/min. The
176 injector was operated in the split mode at 1:10 ratio. The injector temperature was 180 °C. The oven
177 temperature was optimised and programmed at 35 °C for 12 min, subsequently increased to 200 °C at
178 6 °C/min and hold for 1 min, with a total time run of 40.5 minutes. The detector temperature was held
179 at 280 °C. Nitrogen (99.999 %) was used as a makeup gas at 60 ml/min. ChemStation software
180 package (version A0903) was used for data acquisition and evaluation. A good separation was
181 achieved under conditions described. A typical chromatogram showing the separation of all the
182 analytes with direct injection is shown in Fig. 3.

183 The extracts were simultaneously analysed in a Varian CP 3800 GC gas chromatograph coupled
184 to an ion trap mass spectrometer detector Varian Saturn 2000 MS (Varian, Sunnyvale, CA, USA). The
185 analytical column was a VF-5ms 30m x 0.25mm x 0.25 μ m film thickness (Varian Iberica). The oven
186 temperature conditions were the same as those used in GC- μ ECD: 35 °C for 12 minutes, increased to
187 200 °C at a rate of 6 °C/min and held for 1 min, with a total run time of 40.5 min. The injector port
188 temperature was set at 220 °C. Helium was used as carrier gas at a constant flow rate of 1.2 mL min⁻¹.
189 The effectiveness of selected GC-MS conditions were tested, considering sensitivity, baseline
190 separation of analytes and peak shapes. Optimum chromatographic conditions allow a good separation
191 of the ten trihalomethanes and the IS.

192 For mass spectrometry detection, ionization was carried out by electronic impact (EI) with a
193 voltage of 70 eV, using full scan mode in the m/z range of 35-650, with an ion source temperature of
194 220 °C and transference line temperature of 280 °C. For the analysis, 1 μ L of sample was injected in
195 splitless mode. The identification of the chloro, bromo and iodo halomethanes was based on
196 comparison with corresponding standard according to their retention times and mass spectra
197 characteristics, complementarily, searching on NIST Mass Spectral Library was performed. For each
198 compound several monitoring ions were selected (Table 1). The mass to charge ions were used for
199 confirmation.

200 **2.5. Method optimization**

201 To find the most favorable conditions for HF-LPME for the simultaneous analysis of 10 THMs
202 (THM10) in water samples, a preliminary screening of the critical variables by univariate optimization
203 was carried out setting the following initial conditions: temperature (30 °C), HF length (7 cm), direct
204 extraction mode, immersion time (2 min), salt addition (0 %), extraction time (25 min), stirring speed
205 (700 rpm), sample volume (20 ml). In a first step, univariate analysis for the selection of extraction

206 solvent, extraction mode and optimization of operation extraction variables such as immersion time,
207 sample volume, stirring speed and addition of salt was applied. Then in a second step, a second-order
208 rotatable Central composite design (RCCD) was applied to optimize the most significant operation
209 variables, extraction time and fiber length. The experiments were performed with ultrapure water
210 spiked with $1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of each analyte. All results were expressed as mean values of two replicates.

211

212 **3. Results and discussion.**

213 In this study we used a hollow fiber device for simultaneous extraction of ten trihalomethanes, in
214 order to check the advantages over other extraction techniques, such as reproducibility, absence of
215 sample carryover (due to the disposable nature of the membranes), simplicity, low analytical time,
216 low cost, high analyte enrichments, high throughput and large pH tolerance range.

217 **3.1 Selection of organic solvent**

218 The extracting solvent in LPME should be immiscible with water and strongly immobilized in the
219 pores of the hollow fiber to prevent leakage, it should provide high partition coefficients for the target
220 analytes to ensure efficient extraction, and low volatility to avoid evaporation during extraction. In
221 addition, it should have a suitable low viscosity to ensure high diffusion coefficients and should be
222 selective towards the analytes of interest [54]. Based on these considerations, five organic solvents
223 were tested to extract the analytes (1-octanol, n-hexane, ethyl acetate, dihexyl ether and toluene). As
224 can be seen in Fig. 2, 1-octanol and n-hexane gave the best results. The experiments showed that n-
225 hexane was lost during the extraction to a larger extent than 1-octanol. Consequently 1-octanol was
226 chosen for further experiments. It was verified that an immersion time of 2 minutes was sufficient to
227 impregnate the pores of the HF because longer times do not increase the extraction efficiency.

228 Although extractions with 1-octanol perform the best result the quantification by GC showed poorly
229 resolved chromatographic peaks, especially for CHBrI_2 . To optimize the resolution of
230 chromatographic peaks, several mixtures of acceptor solvent with other ones were tested, obtaining
231 improvements in the resolution but with reduced peak areas. Very good results were obtained by
232 diluting the extract obtained with n-hexane at ratio 20:80 (extract: n-hexane) Fig. 3.

233 **3.2 Extraction mode**

234 Direct and headspace extractions were compared using liquid hollow fiber membranes with $1 \mu\text{g}$
235 L^{-1} spiked THM10 water samples using 1-octanol as extracting solvent. In Fig.2 can be seen that
236 extraction is higher using direct extraction mode that was chosen for further experiments.

237 **3.3. Stirring speed**

238 The stirring speed agitation accelerate the mass transfer of extracted analytes from the sample to
239 the organic solvent and reduce the time to reach equilibrium. To estimate the influence of this
240 variable, several values were tested from 0 to 1500 rpm. The Fig. 4 shows that relative area of the
241 analytes increased with the stirring speed, although above 1500 rpm decreased. The extraction of
242 regulated THMs is favored by low stirring speed, obtaining the best results in the range of 0 to 200
243 rpm. However, the best results of I-THMs were obtained with speeds between 500 and 900 rpm.
244 Therefore, a compromise solution was adopted weighting the values obtained with a speed of 900
245 rpm.

246 3.4. Salt addition

247 Salt addition to the sample can reduce the amount of water available to dissolve the analytes due
248 to the formation of hydration spheres around the ionic salt molecules and can improve the extraction
249 efficiency of target analytes into the organic phase. In addition, salt can prevent loss of solvent from
250 HF [55-58]. Different percentages of NaCl and NaSO₄ from 0% to 20% (w/v) were studied; the best
251 results were obtained with NaSO₄.

252 As shown in Fig. 5 the addition of salt (20%) increased peak areas of the regulated THMs,
253 especially TCM and BDCM (Fig.5A), however did not improve peak areas I-THMs (Fig. 5B). The
254 weighted means (Fig. 5W) confirm that the addition of salt at about 20% did not improve the
255 simultaneous extraction of THM10. According to this salt was not used in subsequent experiments.

256 3.5. Experimental design. Multivariate optimization

257 A rotatable second-order central composite design (RCCD) was applied, using MINITAB[®] Release
258 15 Statistical Software (State College, PA, USA) [59] and some home-made programs written in
259 QUICKBASIC, to study the effect of three independent variables: extraction time (*tm*), temperature of
260 the extraction (*T*) and HF length (*L*).

261 The CCD consists in a 2^k (k = number of variables) full factorial design augmented with $2k$ vertices of
262 a cross-polytope (star points) positioned on the coordinate axes of the factorial space and C (number
263 of replicates) points at the center of the design, $(0,0,\dots,0)$. For three factors, the resulting points are
264 $(\pm\alpha,0,0)$, $(0,\pm\alpha,0)$ and $(0,0,\pm\alpha)$, where α is the distance (star arm) from the center of the design to a
265 star point. This implies performing $2^k + 2k + C$ experiments. We applied a rotatable CCD variant
266 method [60,61] in which the variance of the predicted response values depends only on the distance
267 from the center of the design and $\alpha = 2^{k/4}$ (k = number of variables). Each variable has five coded
268 levels $(-\alpha, -1, 0, 1, \alpha)$. Star arms $-\alpha$ and α are the minimum and maximum value of the factor in the

269 common working range. The experimental design RCCD for $K = 3$ and $C = 3$ requires 17 random
 270 trials to avoid systematic errors (Table S2).

271 The response (relative areas peak) of the dix trihalomethanes obtained in the different
 272 experiments (RCCD) carried out by HF-LPME for the optimization is shown in Table 2. Results for
 273 the experimental design, a multilinear regression was applied obtaining reduced models of polynomial
 274 equations representing the relationship between variables and responses Table 3. A significant assay
 275 for the regression coefficients was performed based on the Student's "t-test", once the standard
 276 deviation of the regression coefficients b_k , $S(b_k)$ is known. The significance of the effect is
 277 demonstrated when the absolute value of $t_k = |b_k| / S(b_k)$ is found to be greater than the critical
 278 tabulated value $t_{critic}(v, P)$ for the v degrees of freedom corresponding to the tested regression
 279 model ($v = \text{number of run} - \text{number of coefficients to be estimated}$) with a P confidence level of 95%
 280 ($p\text{-value} > 0.05$). In all simplified models obtained for the different analytes a significant positive
 281 effect of the three variables studied were observed; therefore conducted to optimize the response by
 282 simultaneous maximization of peak areas of all the analytes studied by determining the Combined
 283 Response. Combined Response is a response variable created as a weighed sum of several responses
 284 according to the following equation:

$$COMB = \sum_i \left\{ K w_i \left| \frac{Y_i - G_i}{R_i} \right| \right\}$$

285 where w_i is a user chosen weight, generally set as unity, Y_i is each response to be optimized and R_i the
 286 range of Y_i . When the responses in the combined response are to be maximized, then $k = 1$ and $G_i =$
 287 minimum ($Y_i - \frac{1}{2} R_i$). Using a home-made routine algorithm, a random search of the surface grid
 288 COMB (tm, T, L) is performed. The maximum of the COMB surface is the simultaneous optimum.
 289 This optimization method has been applied in several studies, with good results [62,63]. The
 290 COMBINED 3D and contour plot showing surface shape against the axis temperature, time and length
 291 is plotted optimum point is displayed in Fig. S2. The optimum value was reached at the following
 292 coordinates: time (tm) = -0.58, temperature (T) = -0.58 and length (L) = 1.3. The optimum values of
 293 the variables resulted to be: 19.2 minutes of extraction time, 27.1 °C of extraction temperature and
 294 10.5 cm of hollow fiber length.

296 3.6. Validation of the method

297 To evaluate the practical applicability of the developed HF LPME-GC/ μ ECD method to drinking
 298 water analysis, the linearity, limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ), repeatability
 299 (intra-day), reproducibility (inter-day), recovery extraction, and enrichment factor were determined.
 300 The linearity was obtained in the range 0.1 to 45 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for regulated THMs and 0.010 to 4 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for

301 I-THMs, considering that I-THMs concentrations in water supply are usually in the range from ng^{-1} to
302 low μg^{-1} (Table S3).

303 The linearity was examined by plotting calibration curves of the relative area (ratio of the peak
304 areas of the analyte to the peak areas of the internal standard) versus the concentration of each analyte.
305 Overall, linearity was very good along the whole evaluated range with the determination coefficients
306 (R^2) ranging from 0.995 to 0.999.

307 The detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) limits, defined as the minimum concentration
308 providing chromatographic signals 3 times ($S/N=3$) or 10 times ($S/N=10$) higher than background
309 noise were obtained in the range 100-1000 ng L^{-1} for regulated THMs and 10-100 ng L^{-1} for I-THMs.
310 The LOD values obtained ranged from 1 ng L^{-1} for CHI_3 to 44 ng L^{-1} for CHCl_3 and from 3 ng L^{-1} for
311 CHI_3 to 65 ng L^{-1} for CHCl_3 for LOQ. LOD results obtained with the new method are very
312 satisfactory, as can be seen in the comparison table (Table 4).

313 The precision of the proposed method was evaluated by determination of the repeatability and
314 reproducibility analyzing water samples spiked with 1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and 0.1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of each trihalomethane.
315 The repeatability was studied by analyzing five water samples in one day. The repeatability values
316 (RSD %) were very good ranging from 6 to 22 % for regulated THMs and from 3 to 12 % for I-
317 THMs. The reproducibility refers to the analysis of 12 samples over 3 different days. The
318 reproducibility (RSD %) was very good ranging from 10 to 18 % for regulated THMs and from 6 to
319 12 % for I-THMs.

320 The extraction recovery was calculated using a tap water fortified at two different concentrations
321 (5 and 20 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for regulated THMs, 0.02 and 0.1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for I-THMs) of each target analyte. These
322 concentrations were selected according to their usual concentration in drinking water; all experiments
323 were carried out in quintuplicate ($n=5$). Results show that the recoveries for regulated THMs were
324 from 97.8 % to 105.2 % and for I-THMs from 96.5 % to 104 % at the spiked levels, with relative
325 standard deviation in the range of 4-10 %.

326 The results of method validation are shown in Table 1, which demonstrate the good applicability
327 of the developed method for simultaneous determination of 10 THMs in water samples.

328 Only the method from S. Allard et al. [50] based on HS-SPME-GC-MS allows the simultaneous
329 analysis of regulated and emerging (iodinated) trihalomethanes (Table 4), however, present work
330 improves the extraction recovery and limits of detection are lower, which reinforces the interest of use
331 HF-LPME to trihalomethanes analysis in waters.

332 **4. Application to water distribution system**

333 The formation mechanisms of regulated THMs, their health effects and treatment technologies
334 have been widely studied; however there are few published studies on I-THMs in spite of their
335 demonstrated negative health effects. Formation of I-THMs are affected by the matrix of water source
336 (especially the presence of COT, Br⁻, I⁻ and pH value), the treatment process and environmental and
337 operational variables (temperature, contact time, disinfectant dose). The presence of I-THMs in water
338 supplies is mainly associated to chloramination treatment, but also to oxidation by ozone, chlorine,
339 potassium permanganate, and chlorine dioxide (Table S3).

340 The method developed was applied to the simultaneous determination of trihalomethanes in
341 seven water distribution systems in the Huelva area (southwest Spain) from May to August of 2014.
342 Sample points were selected to evaluate the formation of the regulated and emerging trihalomethanes
343 under different conditions of water treatment process, raw water source and distribución system.
344 Water samples analyzed had different origins: Surface water of Chanza reservoir, treated in Aljaraque
345 WTP using conventional treatment and Lepe WTP (with both conventional treatment and advanced
346 treatment process), surface water of small reservoirs (Jarrama, Encinasola and CSBartolomé) with
347 conventional treatment, and water from underground sources with disinfection treatment (Jabugo and
348 Hinojales). Samples of water distribution systems of Lepe and Rio Tinto in sampling point located to
349 distance of 2-45 km from the WTP, and water retention times between 23 and 73 hours were taken.
350 Sample collection, configurations and features of the seven distribution system studied are shown in
351 Fig. S1 and Table S1. Samples were analyzed in triplicate. The results obtained are shown in Table 5.

352 Concentrations of regulated THMs in water from WTP fed with surface water (S1, S2, S3, S4,
353 S6) ranged from 36.2 and 26.4 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. Minor concentrations of regulated THMs (2.4-9.4 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) were
354 observed in groundwater WTPs (S7, S8) or mixture (S5). When water is oxidized with potassium
355 permanganate, chloroform concentration was higher (41-72 % of total regulated THMs), however
356 when ozonation was used, concentration of brominated and chlorobrominated trihalomethanes were
357 higher than chlorinated ones, accounting for 73 % of the total regulated THMs. The bromoform
358 concentration was higher in waters oxidized with ozone (5.9 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) than that with permanganate (1.2
359 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$). Regulated THMs concentrations increase in the distribution systems, affected by
360 rechlorination processes and increase with contact time.

361 In samples oxidized with potassium permanganate (S1, S2, S4, S5, S6) the I-THMs were detected
362 at low concentrations (\sum I-THM ranged 17 to 4 ng L^{-1}). The species identified were CHCl_2I (3-18 ng
363 L^{-1}), CHCl_2 (8-12 ng L^{-1}), CHBr_2 (2-6 ng L^{-1}), CHBrClI (4-7 ng L^{-1}) and CHI_3 (1-6 ng L^{-1}). The
364 CHBr_2I was not detected in any sample. The behavior of iodinated species in the distribution system is
365 different to regulated THMs, a slight increase in the concentration of CHCl_2I was observed in samples
366 from reservoirs, probably due to rechlorination treatment. The CHI_3 were not detected in reservoir

367 samples, since increased contact time favors the oxidation of iodide to iodate. The highest
368 concentration of I-THMs (Σ I-THM: 126.9 ng L⁻¹) was obtained in S3 that uses a combination of
369 ozone and granular activate carbon filters treatment. Only two of the six possible iodinated
370 compounds were identified in this sample, CHCl₂I (43.0 ng L⁻¹) and CHBrClI (83.9 ng L⁻¹). However,
371 only CHCl₂I was identified in the distribution system, with decreasing concentrations depending on
372 contact time and distance from WTP to distribution reservoir.

373 Finally, in the two samples from water supply of underground origin (S7 and S8) I-THMs were not
374 detected.

375 **5. Conclusion**

376 A new analytical method based on HF-LPME and GC- μ ECD for the simultaneous determination
377 of ten trihalomethanes (regulated and emergent) in drinking water was studied for the first time. The
378 different parameters affecting the HF-LPME extraction were optimized with a rotatable second-order
379 central composite multivariate design (RCCD). The analytical performance of the optimized
380 procedure was evaluated and good linearity, reproducibility and accuracy was obtained together to
381 low detection and quantification limits. The method allows fast extraction and high pre-concentration
382 of analytes, reduction of organic solvent, elimination of carry-over effects using disposable fibers and
383 high applicability to different water matrices The analytical approach is applicable to trace analysis (at
384 ng L⁻¹ levels) of conventional and emerging trihalomethanes in drinking water reservoir and WTPs.

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391

392 **References**

- 393 [1] S.D. Richardson, M.J.Plewa, E.D. Wagner, R. Schoeny, D.M. Demarini, Occurrence, genotoxicity,
394 genotoxicity, and carcinogenicity of regulated and emerging disinfection by-products in drinking water: a
395 review and roadmap for research, *Mutat. Res.* 636 (2007) 178-242
- 396 [2] C.M.Villanueva, K.P. Cantor, J.O. Grimalt, N. Malats, D. Silverman, A. Tardn R. Garcia-Closas, C. Serra,
397 A. Carrato, G. Castaño-Vinyals, R. Marcos, N. Rothamn, F.X Real, M. Dosemeci, M. Kogevinas, Bladder

- 398 cancer and exposure to water disinfection by-products through ingestion, bathing, showering, and swimming
399 in pools, *Am. J. Epidemiol* 165 (2007) 148-156
- 400 [3] W.D. King, L.D. Marrett, C.G. Woolcott, Case-control study of colon and rectal cancers and chlorination by-
401 products in treated water. *Cancer Epidemiol. Biomarkers Prev.* 9 (2000) 813-818
- 402 [4] R.J. Bull, L.S. Birnbaum, K.P. Cantor, J.G. Rose, B.E. Butterworth, R. Pegram, J. Tuomisto, Water
403 Chlorination: Essential Process or Cancer Hazard?, *Fundam. Appl. Toxicol* 28 (1995) 155-166
- 404 [5] M. Koivusalo, J.J. Jaakkola, T. Vartiainen, T. Hakulinen, S. Karjalainen, E. Pukkala, J. Tuomisto, Drinking
405 water mutagenicity and gastrointestinal and urinary tract cancers: An ecological study in Finland, *Am. J.*
406 *Public Health* 84 (1994) 1223-1228
- 407 [6] K. Waller, S.H. Swan, G. DeLoenze, B. Hopkins, Trihalomethanes in drinking water and spontaneous
408 abortion, *Epidemiology* 9 (1998) 134-140
- 409 [7] C.H. Jeong, E.D. Wagner, V.R. Siebert, S. Anduri, S.D. Richardson, E.J. Daiber, A.B. McKague, M.
410 Kogevinas, C.M. Villanueva, E.H. Goslan, W. Luo, L.M. Isabelle, J.F. Pankow, R. Grazuleviciene, S.
411 Cordier, S.C. Edwards, E. Righi, M.J. Nieuwenhuijsen, M.J. Plewa, Occurrence and toxicity of
412 disinfection byproducts in European drinking waters in relation with the HIWATE epidemiology study,
413 *Environ Sci. Technol.* 46 (2012) 12120-12128
- 414 [8] R.D. Morris, A.M. Audet, I.F. Angelillo, T.C. Chalmers, and E. Mosteller, Chlorination, chlorination by-
415 products, and cancer: A meta-analysis, *Am. J. Public. Health* 82 (1992) 955-963
- 416 [9] Agency U.S.E.P.A. National Primary Drinking Water Regulations. EPA 816-F-09-004 (2009)
- 417 [10] Organization, W.H., Guidelines for drinking-water quality. Geneva. World Health Organization (2011) 632
- 418 [11] A. Hebert, D. Forestier, D. Lenes, D. Benanou, S. Jacob, C. Arfi, L. Lambolez, Y. Levi, Innovative method
419 for prioritizing emerging disinfection by-products (DBPs) in drinking water on the basis of their potential
420 impact on public health, *Water Res.* 44 (2010) 3147-3165
- 421 [12] S.D. Richardson, F. Fasano, J.J. Ellington, F.G. Chumley, K.M. Buettner, J.J. Evans, B.C. Blount,
422 L.K. Silva, T.J. Waite, G.W. Luther, A.B. McKague, R.J. Miltner, E.D. Wagner and M.J. Plewa, Occurrence
423 and mammalian cell toxicity of iodinated disinfection byproducts in drinking water, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*
424 42 (2008) 8330-8338
- 425 [13] M.J. Plewa, E.D. Wagner, Quantitative comparative mammalian cell cytotoxicity and genotoxicity of
426 selected classes of drinking water disinfection by-product, *Am. Water Works Res. Found. : Denver, CO,*
427 (2008).
- 428 [14] B. Cancho, C. Fabrellas, A. Diaz, and F. Ventura. Determination of the odor threshold concentrations of
429 iodinated trihalomethanes in drinking water, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 49 (2001) 1881-1884.
- 430 [15] A.D. Nikolaou, T.D. Lekkas, S.K. Goufopoulos, M.N. Kostopoulou, Application of different analytical
431 methods for determination of volatile chlorination by-products in drinking water. *Talanta* 56 (2002), 717-
432 726.
- 433 [16] EPA, EPA Method 551.1. Determination of chlorinated disinfection by-products, chlorinated solvents, and
434 halogenated pesticides/herbicides in drinking water by liquid-liquid extraction and gas chromatograph with

- 435 electron capture detection, USEPA, Office of Water. Technical Support Center, 26 W, Martin Luther King
436 Drive, Cincinnati (1998) OH 45268.
- 437 [17] G. Castello, T.C. Gerbino, S. Kantiz, Sensitivity and linearity of headspace and liquid-liquid extraction
438 techniques for gas chromatographic analysis of halocarbons in water, *J. Chromatogr. A* 351 (1986) 165.
- 439 [18] S.K. Golfinopoulos, T.D. Lekkas, A.D. Nikolaou, Comparison of methods for determination of volatile
440 organic compounds in drinking water, *Chemosphere* 45 (2001) 275.
- 441 [19] A.D. Nikolaou, T.D. Lekkas, S.K. Golfinopoulos, M.N. Kostopoulou, Application of different analytical
442 methods for determination of volatile chlorination by-products in drinking water. *Talanta* 56(2002), 717–
443 726.
- 444 [20]. A.S. Alloniera, M. Khalanskia, A. Bermondb, V. Camel, Determination of trihalomethanes in chlorinated
445 sea water samples using a purge-and-trap system coupled to gas chromatography. *Talanta* 51 (2000) 467–
446 477
- 447 [21] L. Zoccolillo, L. Amendola, C. Cafaro, S. Insogna. Improved analysis of volatile halogenated
448 hydrocarbons in water by purge-and-trap with gas chromatography and mass spectrometric detection,
449 *Journal of Chromatography A*, 1077 (2005) 181–187
- 450 [22] A. Lara-Gonzalo, J. E. Sánchez-Uría, E. Segovia-García, A. Sanz-Medel, Critical comparison of
451 automated purge and trap and solid-phase microextraction for routine determination of volatile organic
452 compounds in drinking waters by GC–MS. *Talanta* 74 (2008) 1455–1462.
- 453 [23] A. Ikem, Measurement of volatile organic compounds in bottled and tap waters by purge and trap GC-MS:
454 are drinking water types different? *J. Food Comp. Anal.* 23 (2010), 70–77.
- 455 [24] F. Ruiz-Bevia, M.J. Fernandez-Torres, M.P. Blasco-Aleman, Purge efficiency in the determination of
456 trihalomethanes in water by purge-and-trap gas chromatography. *Anal. Chim. Acta* 632 (2009) 304–314.
- 457 [25] M. Biziuk, J. Namienik, J. Czerwifiski, D. Gorlo, B. Makuch, W. Janicki, Z. Polkowska, L. Wolska
458 Occurrence and determination of organic pollutants in tap and surface waters of the Gdafisk district.
459 *Journal of Chromatography A*, 733 (1996) 171-183
- 460 [26] L. Wolska, C. Olszewska, M. Turska, B. Zygmunt, J. Namiesnik. Volatile and semivolatile organo-
461 halogen trace analysis in surface water by direct aqueous injection GC-ECD, *Chemosphere*, 37 (1998) 13,
462 2645-2651.
- 463 [27] S. M. Pyle and D.F. Gurka. Volatile organic analysis by direct aqueous injection. *Talanta* 41 (1994) 1845-
464 1852.
- 465 [28] A. Serrano, M. Gallego, Rapid determination of total trihalomethanes index in drinking water. *J.*
466 *Chromatogr. A* 1154(2007) 26–33.
- 467 [29] S. Golfinopoulos, T.D. Lekkas, A.D. Nikolaou, Comparison of methods for determination of volatile
468 organic compounds in drinking water *Chemosphere* 45 (2001), 275-284
- 469 [30] J. Kuivinen, H. Johnsson, Determination of trihalomethanes and some chlorinated solvents in drinking
470 water by headspace technique with capillary column gas-chromatography *Water Research* 33 (1999) 1201-
471 1208

- 472 [31] A. Lara-Gonzalo, J.E. Sánchez-Uría, E. Segovia-García, A. Sanz-Medel, Critical comparison of automated
473 purge and trap and solid-phase microextraction for routine determination of volatile organic compounds in
474 drinking waters by GC–MS. *Talanta*, 74 (2008) 1455–1462.
- 475 [32] J. Merib, V. Simão, A. Neves, E. Carasek, Simultaneous determination of trihalomethanes and
476 organochlorine pesticides in water samples by direct immersion-headspace-solid phase microextraction,
477 *Journal of Chromatography A* (2013) 1321, 30–37
- 478 [33] M.L. Di Gioia, A. Leggio, A. Le Pera, A. Liguori, A. Napoli, C. Siciliano, SPE-GC-MS analysis of
479 chloroform in drinking water. *Chromatogr.* 60 (2004) 319–322.
- 480 [34] M. Bahri, M.R. Driss, Development of solid-phase microextraction for the determination of
481 trihalomethanes in drinking water from Bizerte, Tunisia. *Desalination* 250 (2010) 414–417.
- 482 [35] D.H. Cho, S.H. Kong, S.G. Oh, Analysis of trihalomethanes in drinking water using headspace-SPME
483 technique with gas chromatography. *Water Res.* 37 (2003) 402–408.
- 484 [36] C.S.A.Sá, R.A.R. Boaventura, I.B. Pereira, Analysis of trihalomethanes in water and air from indoor
485 swimming pools using HS-SPME/GC/ECD. *J. Environ. Sci. Health, Part A: Toxic/Hazard. Subst.*
486 *Environ. Eng.* 46 (2011) 355–363.
- 487 [37] P.M. San Juan, J.D. Carrillo, M. T. Tena, Fibre selection based on an overall analytical feature comparison
488 for the solid-phase microextraction of trihalomethanes from drinking water, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1139 (2007)
489 27–35.
- 490 [38] A. Tor, M.E. Aydin, Application of liquid-phase microextraction to the analysis of trihalomethanes in
491 water. *Anal. Chim. Acta* 575 (2006) 138–143.
- 492 [39] A. Tor, M.E. Aydin, Application of liquid-phase microextraction to the analysis of trihalomethanes in
493 water, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 575 (2006) 138-143
- 494 [40] R.-S. Zhao, W.-J. Lao, X.-B. Xu, Headspace liquid-phase microextraction of trihalomethanes in drinking
495 water and their gas chromatographic determination, *Talanta* 62 (2004) 751-756
- 496 [41] C.C. Chang, G.R. Her, On-line monitoring trihalomethanes in chlorinated water by membrane
497 introduction–fast gas chromatography mass–spectrometry (2000) *J Chromatogr A* 893:169–175
- 498 [42] N. Vora-adisak, P. Varanusupakul, A simple supported liquid hollow fiber membrane microextraction for
499 sample preparation of trihalomethanes in water samples. *J. Chromatogr. A* 1121(2006) 236– 241.
- 500 [43] M. Moreano-Rosero, M. Aguirre, D. Pezo, G. Taborda, C. Dussán, C. Nerin, Solventless Microextraction
501 Techniques for Determination of Trihalomethanes by Gas Chromatography in Drinking Water. *Water Air*
502 *Soil Pollut.* 223 (2012) 667–678.
- 503 [44] R.R. Kozani, Y. Assadi, F. Shemirani, M.R. Milani-Hosseini, M.R. Jamali, Determination of
504 trihalomethanes in drinking water by dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction then gas chromatography
505 with electron-capture detection, *Chromatogr.* 66 (2007) 81-86
- 506 [45] S. Shegefti, H. Sereshti, S. Samadi Measurement of chloroform in swimming pools' waters and swimmers'
507 blood Iran. *J. Publ. Health*, 38 (2009) 103–110

- 508 [46] R.C. Hansson, M.J. Henderson, P. Jack, R. Taylor, Iodoform taste complaints in chloramination. *Water*
509 *Res.* 21 (1987) 1265-1271
- 510 [47] B. Cancho, F. Ventura, M. Galceran, A. Díaz, S. Ricart, Determination, synthesis and survey of iodinated
511 trihalomethanes in water treatment processes, *Wat. Research* 34 (2000) 3380-3390
- 512 [48] B. Cancho, F. Ventura, M.T. Galceran. Solid-phase microextraction for the determination of iodinated
513 trihalomethanes in drinking water, *J. Chromatogr. A* 841 (1999) 197-206.
- 514 [49] Q. Luo, X. Chen, Z. Weib, X. Xub, D. Wang, Z. Wang, Simultaneous and high-throughput analysis of
515 iodo-trihalomethanes, haloacetonitriles, and halonitromethanes in drinking water using solid-phase
516 microextraction/gas chromatography-mass spectrometry: an optimization of sample preparation, *Journal of*
517 *Chromatography A* 1365 (2014) 45–53
- 518 [50] S. Allard, J.W. Charrois, C.A. Joll, A. Heitz, Simultaneous analysis of 10 trihalomethanes at nanogram per
519 liter level in water using solid-phase microextraction and gas chromatography mass-spectrometry, *J.*
520 *Chromatogr. A* 1238 (2012) 15-21
- 521 [51] S. Pedersen-Bjergaard, K.E. Rasmussen, Liquid-liquid-liquid microextraction for sample preparation of
522 biological fluids prior to capillary electrophoresis, *Anal. Chem.* 71 (1999) 2650-2656
- 523 [52] A. Sarafraz-Yazdi, A. Amiri, Liquid-phase microextraction, *Trends Anal. Chem.* 29 (2010) 1-14
- 524 [53] J. Manso, E. Larsson, J.A. Johsson, Determination of 4'-isobutylacetophenone and other transformation
525 products of anti-inflammatory drugs in water and sludge from five wastewater treatment plants in Sweden
526 by hollow fiber liquid phase microextraction and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry, *Talanta* 125
527 (2014) 87-93
- 528 [54] M. Ghambarian, Y. Yamini, A. Esrafil. Developments in hollow fiber based liquid-phase microextraction:
529 Principles and applications, *Microchim. Acta.* 177 (2012) 271-294
- 530 [55] P-S. Chen, S-D. Huang, Determination of ethoprop, diazinon, disulfoton and fenthion using dynamic
531 hollow fiber-protected liquid-phase microextraction coupled with gas chromatography-mass spectrometry,
532 *Talanta*, 69 (2006) 669-675
- 533 [56] Howard, P. H., Meylan. W. M., "Handbook of Physical Properties of Organic Chemicals" Boca Raton:
534 CRC Press-Lewis Publishers (ed.) (1997)
- 535 [57] C. Basheer, R. Balasubramanian, H.K. Lee, Determination of organic micropollutants in rainwater using
536 hollow fiber membrane/liquid-phase microextraction combined with gas chromatography-mass
537 spectrometry *J. Chromatogr. A* 1016 (2003) 11- 20
- 538 [58] C. Basheer, H.K. Lee, J.P. Obbard, Application of liquid-phase microextraction and gas chromatography-
539 mass spectrometry for the determination of polychlorinated biphenyls in blood plasma. *J. Chromatogr. A*
540 1022 (2004) 161-169
- 541 [59] MINITAB R ® Release 16 Statistical Software for Windows, 2010, Minitab Inc., State College, PA, USA.
- 542 [60] G.E.P. Box, K.B. Wilson, On the Experimental Attainment of Optimum Conditions, *J. Royal Stat. Soc.*
543 *Series B* 13 (1951) 1-45

- 544 [61] G.E.P. Box, W.G. Hunter, J.S. Hunter, Statistics for Experimenters; An introduction to Design, Data
 545 Analysis and Model Building. Willey Series in Probability and Mathematical Statistics, John Wiley &
 546 Sons Publishers (1978)
- 547 [62] J.L. Gómez-Ariza, T. García-Barrera, F. Lorenzo, A. Gustavo-González, Optimisation of a pressurised
 548 liquid extraction method for haloanisoles in cork stoppers, Anal. Chim. Acta 540 (2005) 17-24
- 549 [63] J.Manso, T.Garcia-Barrera, J.L.Gómez-Ariza, New home-made assembly for hollow-fibre membrane
 550 extraction of persistent organic pollutants from real world samples, J.Chromatogr A 1218 (2011) 7923-
 551 7935

552 Figure captions

553 Fig. 1 Extraction device for HF-LPME

554 Fig. 2 Chromatographic peak area (average n=2) for the selection of organic solvent and extraction mode.
 555 (A) Regulated THMs: CHCl₃ (TCM), CHCl₂Br (BDCM), CHClBr₂ (BDCM) and CHBr₃ (TBM).
 556 (B) Unregulated I-THMs: CHCl₂I (DCIM), CHBrClI (BCIM), CHBr₂I (DBIM), CHClI₂ (CDIM), CHBrI₂
 557 (BDIM) and CHI₃ (IF), using three extraction solvents: 1-Octanol (OCT), n-Hexane (HEX) and Heptane
 558 (HEP), and two extraction mode: Direct extraction (DE) and head space (HS).
 559 (W) Weighted peak area from the extraction of regulated THM (THM4), unregulated I-THM (I-THM),
 560 and total THMs (THM10)

561 Fig. 3 GC- μ ECD chromatogram obtained from a standard solution at 1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of each regulated THM and
 562 0.1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of each I-THM, using HF-LPME

563 Fig. 4 Influence of stirring speed in the extraction of THMs: (A) regulated THMs; (B) emerging I-THMs;
 564 (C) total THMs

565 Fig. 5 Effect of the addition of sodium sulfate on the chromatographic peak area: (A) regulated THM; (B)
 566 unregulated iodo-THM

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570 Tables.

571 Table 1 Method validation

Analyte	m/z ions	E _e	Range ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	R ²	LOD (ng L^{-1})	LOQ (ng L^{-1})	Repeatability (% n=5)		Reproducibility (% n=12)	
							100 ng L^{-1}	1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	100 ng L^{-1}	1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$
CHCl ₃	83+85	21	0.1-45	0.999	44	65	22	9	18	7
CHBrCl ₂	129+85+127	32	0.1-45	0.999	3	5	12	6	13	3
CHClBr ₂	129+127	52	0.1-45	0.999	7	13	7	4	10	4
CHBr ₃	173+171	56	0.1-45	0.999	3	6	6	4	10	3
CHCl ₂ I	175+83	618	0.010-4	0.995	1	4	7	3	7	5
CHBrClI	256+129+131	311	0.010-4	0.998	3	12	3	2	8	7
CHBr ₂ I	302+219	469	0.010-4	0.996	3	10	5	3	6	6

CHCl ₂	175+302	574	0.010-4	0.996	1	4	6	6	8	7
CHBrI ₂	219+348	789	0.010-4	0.999	1	3	10	8	12	10
CHI ₃	394+267	1016	0.010-4	0.999	1	4	12	10	10	10

572 E_e = Enrichment factor = Ratio of the concentration of analyte in the acceptor phase (c_a) divided by the initial concentration in
 573 the sample before extraction (c_d). $E_e = c_a / c_d$

574 m/z ions: mass to charge ratio of specific fragments used for selected-ion monitoring MS analysis.

575

576 Table 2 Relative response of peak area in RCCD experiment

	CHCl ₃	CHBrCl ₂	CHClBr ₂	CHCl ₂ I	CHBr ₃	CHBrClI	CHBr ₂ I	CHClI ₂	CHBrI ₂	CHI ₃
C1	207	473	951	2236	824	1602	2286	8410	10613	17500
C2	188	353	581	1595	512	1127	1517	4960	6764	11483
C3	113	212	349	958	308	677	911	2892	4018	6830
C4	243	457	750	2060	661	1456	1960	6421	8982	17924
C5	525	987	1622	4455	1430	3150	4238	17159	24698	46660
C6	337	634	1042	2861	919	2023	2722	10229	14912	28041
C7	421	793	1303	3578	1149	2529	3404	9572	12551	23185
C8	290	546	898	2465	791	1743	2345	7572	10424	19577
C9	278	523	859	2359	757	1668	2244	6468	8219	11892
C10	237	446	734	2014	647	1424	1916	5438	7394	12940
C11	348	656	1077	2958	950	2091	2814	7452	8666	15857
C12	307	578	950	2609	837	1844	2482	7262	8770	13757
C13	226	425	698	1917	616	1356	1824	5313	6678	9830
C14	560	1054	1732	4756	1527	3363	4525	15625	22057	40425
C15	557	1045	1670	3501	1225	2463	2909	9992	11809	18376
C16	537	890	1566	3547	1244	2797	3182	9836	11356	17334
C17	504	964	1570	3776	1317	2835	3691	9842	11550	17900

577

578 Table 3 Reduced models

Model Equation	R ² (%)	p
$CHCl_3 = 533.96 - 20.23*tm - 18.92*T + 101.44*L - 102.36*tm^2 - 77.52*T^2 - 54.47*L^2 + 25.68*tm*T - 53.68*tm*L$	98.40	0.000
$CHBrCl_2 = 968.52 - 44.22*tm + 184.79*L - 178.1*tm^2 - 131.36*T^2 - 87.97*L^2 + 58.81*tm*T - 90.55*tm*L$	97.03	0.000
$CHClBr_2 = 1604.08 - 85.39*tm - 81.34*T + 290.85*L - 292.65*tm^2 - 215.86*T^2 - 144.57*L^2 + 118.38*tm*T - 127.01*tm*L$	96.56	0.000
$CHCl_2I = 3620.33 - 206.9*tm - 195.77*T + 826.36*L - 545.13*tm^2 - 334.26*T^2 - 277.98*tm*T - 395.93*tm*L$	96.7	0.002
$CHBr_3 = 1264.49 - 74.2*tm - 70.63*T + 257.50*L - 207.27*tm^2 - 139.58*T^2 - 76.73*L^2 + 102.52*tm*T - 113.82*tm*L$	96.01	0.001
$CHBrClI = 2707.35 - 147.86*tm + 582.62*L - 435.01*tm^2 - 285.92*T^2 + 199.23*tm*T - 277.2*tm*L$	96.22	0.001
$CHBr_2I = 3272.02 + 774.51*L - 455.85*tm^2 - 255.23*T^2 - 356.78*tm*L$	94.04	0.016
$CHClI_2 = 9851.7 - 1070.6*T + 2869.7*L - 1259.9*tm^2 + 1488.6*tm*T$	93.3	0.043
$CHBrI_2 = 11481.4 - 1525.7*T + 4252.3*L + 2059*tm*T$	92.2	0.001
$CHI_3 = 17613 - 2906.9*T + 8433.9*L + 3448.4*L^2 + 4015.2*tm*T$	92.7	0.025

579 Equation model: $y = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_{0i} X_i + \sum \beta_{ii} X_i^2 + \sum \beta_{ij} X_i X_j$; response: peak area of each THM. Variable: tm (extraction
 580 time), T (extraction temperature °C), L (HF length).

581

582
583
584 Table 4 Comparison of detection limits and recoveries of developed method with others previously reported

Instrumental Method	Extraction procedure	Regulated THM		I-THMs		Ref.
		Recovery %	LOD $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	Recovery %	LOD $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	
LLE-GC-ECD	2 ml glass-distilled; n-hexane	103.0-111.0	0.025-0.05			[18]
LLE-GC-ECD	2 ml MTBE; 6gr NaSO ₄	87.6-112.8	0.010-0.007			[19]
LLE-GC-MS	2 ml MBTE; 6gr NaSO ₄	87.6-112.8	0.010-0.030			[19]
HS-LPME-GC-ECD	1-Octanol, 15ml, HS, 40ml vial, 10min. extract., 800rpm, 20°C. 0.3gr/ml NaCl	108.4-112	0.15-0.40			[40]
LPME-GC-ECD	n-hexane,t: 5min, stirring rate 600rpm, T: 25°C, NaCl 3M	73.0-78.0	0.23-0.45			[39]
HF-LPME-GC-ECD	Accurel Q 3/2 PP HF, ϕ 600 μm ; e:200 μm ; 35°C, no stirring, no salt, 30 min., long: 8.5cm. 1-octanol	98.0-105.0	0.010-0.200			[42]
HS-SPME-GC- μ ECD	PDMS, T: 30-45°C, t: 20-40min. Desorption T: 200-300°C,t:2-6min.	74.7-120.9	0.059-0.317			[43]
HF-LPME-GC-ECD	Accurel PP ϕ 330 μm ; e:150 μm ; L:110mm, T:25-50°C, t:5-20min; 0-10%salt; 1-octanol.	80.3-104.2	0.018-0.049			[43]
DLLME-GC-ECD	0.5ml acetone (disperser solvent) whit 20 mL carbon disulfide (extraction solvent)	95.0-107.8	0.05-0.040			[44]
LLE-GC-ECD	2 ml glass-distilled; MTBE			100.0-104.0	0.010-0.030	[47]
HS-SPME-GC-ECD	65 μm Carbowax-divinylbenzene fiber.			83.3-90.0	0.0012-0.030	[48]
HS-SPME-GC-MS	CAR/PDMS/DVB,t 30min, T 40°C			80.9-93.0	0.002-0.070	[49]
HS-SPME-GC-MS	CAR/PDMS/DVB,t 15min, T 70°C	84.0-103.0	0.003-0.020	84.0-103.0	0.003-0.008	[50]
HF-LPME-GC-ECD	Accurel Q 3/2 PP HF ϕ 600 μm ; e:200 μm , 27.1°C, 900rpm, no salt, 19.2 min., 10.5cm. 1-octanol.	97.8-105.2	0.003-0.044	96.5-104.0	0.001-0.003	This work

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588 Table 5. Presence of 10 THMs (n=3) in different water distribution systems from Huelva province (southwest Spain).

N°	CHCl ₃ (µgL ⁻¹)	CHBrCl ₂ (µgL ⁻¹)	CHBr ₂ Cl (µgL ⁻¹)	CHBr ₃ (µgL ⁻¹)	∑THMs (µgL ⁻¹)	CHCl ₂ I (ngL ⁻¹)	CHBrClI (ngL ⁻¹)	CHBr ₂ I (ngL ⁻¹)	CHClI ₂ (ngL ⁻¹)	CHBrI ₂ (ngL ⁻¹)	CHI ₃ (ngL ⁻¹)	∑I-THM (ngL ⁻¹)
S1	12.2	9.3	5.5	0.8	27.8	18	<LOD	<LOD	12	6	1	37
S2	11.8	8.7	6.8	1.2	28.5	9	7	<LOD	9	<LOD	2	27
S2.1	25.1	18.7	9.3	1.3	54.4	16	6	<LOD	12	5	<LOD	39
S3	3.9	12.0	16.4	5.9	36.2	43.0	83.9	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	126.9
S3.1	26.4	18.7	19.6	5.6	70.3	20.8	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	20.8
S3.2	30.8	25.4	20.6	5.4	82.2	11.7	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	11.7
S4	19.9	7.3	1.8	0.2	29.2	15	6	<LOD	12	5	<LOD	38
S4.1	40.7	14.1	4.7	0.6	60.1	18	4	<LOD	12	5	6	45
S5	2.0	0.1	0.1	0.2	2.4	7	4	<LOD	8	2	<LOD	21
S6	18.9	5.6	1.7	0.2	26.4	3	<LOD	<LOD	9	5	<LOD	17
S7	4.3	0.6	1.4	2.1	8.4	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
S8	3.9	1.2	2.1	2.2	9.4	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD

Fig 2

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Fig 3

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Fig 4

Fig 5

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